

from ethanol to furnish 1a (85%), m.p. 110°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700 (C=O ester), 1600 (C=N) and 1050 cm^{-1} (C-O-C); δ 1.19 (3H, t, CH_3 ester), 2.15 (3H, s, N=C- CH_3), 3.5 (2H, s, CH_2CO), 4.2 (2H, q, CH_2 ester), 6.8-7.5 (4H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, s, CONH exchangeable with D_2O).

1-Substituted-benzamidyl|aryloxamidyl-3-chloro-4-carboethoxymethylmethyl-2-aztidinone (2): To a solution of 1a (3.23 g, 0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.02 mol) in dioxane (20 ml) was added chloroacetyl chloride (0.02 mol) dropwise with stirring in cold at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min and then refluxed for 3 h. On cooling, the resulting solid was removed by filtration and the filtrate triturated with ether-petroleum ether (1:1) until it solidified. The solid was recrystallised from a mixture of ethanol and water to give 2a (75%), m.p. 220°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3300-3200 (NH), 1720 (C=O ester) and 1660 cm^{-1} (CONH); δ 1.1 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.3 (3H, t, CH_3 ester), 3.5 (2H, s, CH_2CO), 4.2 (2H, q, CH_2 ester), 5.6 (1H, s, CHCl), 7.4-7.5 (2H, d, J_{ortho} 9 Hz, C_6 -H and C_5 -H) and 7.6-7.7 (2H, d, J_{ortho} 9 Hz, C_6 -H and C_5 -H)

N_2 -Substituted-1,2-diazo-4-chloro-5-methyl-3,7-dioxobicyclo[3,2,0]heptane: A solution of 2a (3.69 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed in *o*-dichlorobenzene (20 ml) for about 5 h and then left overnight. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to yield 3a (74%), m.p. 158°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1660 (CONH) and 1600 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ 1.1 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.5 (2H, s, CH_2CO), 5.5 (1H, s, CHCl), 7.3-7.4 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, C_6 -H and C_5 -H) and 7.6-7.7 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, C_6 -H and C_5 -H).

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Synthesis of 4-(5-Substituted-arylidine-4-thiazolidinone-2-thione)-6,8-substituted-quinazolines as Potential Anthelmintic Agents

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A series of substituted-quinazolines have been synthesised and found to exhibit anthelmintic activity against *Hymenolepis nana* in rats.

Several compounds containing quinazolone nucleus have recently been introduced for the treatment of infection caused by different intestinal nematodes and cestodes¹. Many 4-thiazolidinone-2-thiones² have been reported to possess broad spectrum of anthelmintic activity. Hence an attempt has been made to synthesise such compounds having both the moieties. The present communication describes the synthesis of 4-(5-substituted-arylidine-4-thiazolidinone-2-thione)-6,8-substituted-quinazolines (3) and their anthelmintic activity. In general, 6,8-substituted-4-chloroquinazolones (1) were prepared by 6,8-substituted-4-quinazolones in presence of PCl_5 and POCl_3 under anhydrous conditions and the intermediate 5-substituted-arylidine-4-thiazolidinone-2-thiones³ (2) were synthesised by refluxing substituted-aldehydes and rhodanines in glacial acetic acid with fused sodium acetate. Condensation of the intermediates 1 and 2 in pyridine gave 4-(5-substituted-arylidine-4-thiazolidinone-2-thione)-6,8-substituted-quinazolines.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3 + DMSO-d_6) on a Varian EM 360 instrument.

4-[5-(3,4-Dimethoxy)arylidine-4-thiazolidinone-2-thione]-6-bromoquinazolinone (3): A mixture of 5-

(3,4-dimethoxyarylidine-4-thiazolidinone-2-thione) (0.01 mol) and 6-bromo-4-chloroquinazoline (0.01 mol) was refluxed in pyridine (20 ml) for 4 h. The excess pyridine was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the mixture poured in ice-cold water. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 219° (Found: C, 58.41; H, 3.2; N, 9.02. $C_{20}H_{14}N_4O_2S_2$ requires: C, 58.82; H, 3.43; N, 9.29%; ν_{max} 1350 (C-N), 1115 (C-S), 675 (C-S), 1600 (C=CH), 1520 (C=N), 1020 (C-O-C of C-OCH₃) and 3300 cm^{-1} (C-H of CH₃); δ 7.5-6.4 (7H, m, ArH and =CH), 7.8 (1H, s, N=CH-N) and 3.9-3.8 (3H, s, 2 × OCH₃ of Ar(OCH₃)₂).

Similarly, other compounds of the series were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 4-5-8,4-SUBSTITUTED-ARYLIDINE-4-THIAZOLIDINONE-2-THIONE-6,8-SUBSTITUTED-QUINAZOLINES (3)

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
X ₁ = X = H					
1.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	210	65
2.	N(OH) ₂	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃	205	50
3.	Cl	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₀ ClN ₄ O ₃	160	50
4.	H	Cl	C ₁₉ H ₁₀ ClN ₄ O ₃	175	45
X ₁ = Br, X = H					
5.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₄ O ₃ S ₂	218	70
6.	N(OH) ₂	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₄ O ₃ S ₂	232	55
7.	Cl	H	C ₁₉ H ₉ BrClN ₄ O ₃ S ₂	220	50
8.	H	Cl	C ₁₉ H ₉ BrClN ₄ O ₃ S ₂	250	55
X ₁ = I, X = H					
9.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ I ₂ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	196	45
10.	N(OH) ₂	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ I ₂ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	240	70
11.	Cl	H	C ₁₉ H ₉ O ₃ I ₂ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	188	70
12.	H	Cl	C ₁₉ H ₉ O ₃ I ₂ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	145	55
X ₁ = X = Br					
13.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	180	50
14.	N(OH) ₂	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	198	52
15.	Cl	H	C ₁₉ H ₉ Br ₂ ClN ₄ O ₃ S ₂	215	55
16.	H	Cl	C ₁₉ H ₉ Br ₂ ClN ₄ O ₃ S ₂	198	55

Anthelmintic activity: The compound were screened for their cestocidal activity against *Hymenolepis nana* infection in rats using the technique of Steward⁸ with slight modifications. The compounds were given orally at doses of 250 mg/kg using 3 rats per experimental group.

Results and Discussion

For anthelmintic activity *in vivo* 12 compounds were tested. The compound having sl. no. 15 (Table 1) showed maximum (65%) activity. The compounds having sl. nos. 3, 5-8, 11 and 14 showed moderate activity (20-50%) and rest of the compounds were inactive.

The data seem to suggest that the introduction of electron-withdrawing groups at R₁ increases the activity whereas that of electron-donating groups at R₁ and R₂ decreases the anthelmintic activity.

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Synthesis of Thiosemicarbazides and Related Compounds as Potential Fungicides

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THIOSEMICARBAZIDES have N-C=S group, which is an essential structural feature responsible for various biological activities^{1,2}. Various substituted-thiadiazoles³ and triazoles^{4,5} are known to exhibit significant biological activities. Keeping these in view and in continuation of our ongoing research for new antifungal agents^{2,4}, the title compounds have been prepared.

Reaction of α -aryloxypropionyl hydrazines and aryl isothiocyanates yielded 1- α -aryloxypropionyl-4-arylothiosemicarbazides (2a-i). Cyclisation of thiosemicarbazides (2a-i) gave 2-arylamino-5- α -aryloxyethyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (3a-i). 3- α -Aryloxyethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (4a-i) were synthesised by refluxing α -aryloxypropionyl hydrazines with aryl isothiocyanates in sodium hydroxide (Scheme 1). Structures of compounds were established by elemental analyses, ir and pmr spectral data.

Fungicidal screening: Twelve compounds were tested for their antifungal activity against *A. niger*,

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